

NOTES

Studies on Mixed Ligand Complexes of Cu(II) with 8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-Sulphonic Acid as Primary Ligand and Glycine, α -Alanine and Phenylalanine as the Secondary Ligands

H. S. VERMA, B. P. SINGH*, S. P. SINGH
and

N. P. S. BISHT

Department of Chemistry, J. V. College, Baraut-250 611
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SURVEY of the existing literature revealed that little has so far been done on the mixed ligand complexes of 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid¹⁻³. A knowledge of stability constants of mixed ligand complexes is of considerable interest due to their higher stability in many cases in comparison to the stability of parent binary complexes and their utility in analytical and biological chemistry. The present paper is a continuation of our earlier work³ and was undertaken with the view to determine the formation constants in the ternary systems involving Cu(II) with 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (HQSA) in presence of equimolar concentration of α -alanine (Ala), phenylalanine (Phe) or glycine (Gly).

Experimental

Materials: Stock solution of copper nitrate (AnalaR, BDH) was prepared and standardized as reported earlier⁴. The solutions of α -amino acids (Gly, Ala and Phe) were prepared in doubly distilled water by direct weighing and their strengths were checked pH-metrically. 8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (HQSA) (recrystallized from water) was weighed out directly for each investigation on account of its low solubility. The potassium nitrate solution (1.0M) and buffer solutions were prepared by dissolving their AnalaR samples in doubly distilled water. The potassium hydroxide was first washed with methanol to make it carbonate free and a standard aqueous solution (0.1M) of it was prepared in the usual manner.

Apparatus and technique: A Systronics pH-meter operated with glass electrode and calomel reference electrode was used. All pH-measurements were taken after standardizing it by potassium hydrogen phthalate and borax buffer solutions. The temperature of the thermostatic bath was maintained at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$. The pH-titrations of the following sets of solutions were carried out in aqueous

medium in the inert atmosphere of purified nitrogen gas:

- (i) 10.00 ml (0.025M) HQSA/Gly/Ala/Phe+5.00 ml (1.00M) KNO_3 +35.00 ml redistilled water.
- (ii) 10.00 ml (0.025M) HQSA/Gly/Ala/Phe+10.00 ml (0.025M) copper nitrate+5.00 ml (1.00M) KNO_3 +25.00 ml redistilled water (1 : 1).
- (iii) 10.00 ml (0.025M) HQSA+10.00 ml (0.025M) Gly/Ala/Phe+10.00 ml (0.025M) copper nitrate+5.00 ml (1.00M) KNO_3 +15.00 ml redistilled water (1 : 1 : 1).

Results and Discussion

Curves 1-4 (Fig. 1) represent the pH-metric titrations of HQSA, Ala, Phe and Gly respectively with potassium hydroxide. The values of their dissociation constants were found the same as reported in the literature⁴⁻⁶. The pH-metric

Fig. 1. pH Titration curves of mixed ligand chelates, Cu(II)-HQSA-Ala/Phe/Gly: 1, HQSA; 2, Ala; 3, Phe; 4, Gly; 5, 6, 7 & 8, Cu(II)-HQSA/Ala/Phe/Gly (1 : 1); 9, 10 & 11, Cu(II)-HQSA-Ala/Phe/Gly (1 : 1 : 1). Arrow indicates the appearance of solid phase.

* For Correspondence.

TABLE 1—DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF LIGANDS AND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF 1 : 1, 1 : 2 AND 1 : 1 : 1 MIXED CHELATES OF COPPER(II)

Ligand	pK_1	pK_2	pK'_1	$\log K_{MA}$	$\log K_{MA_2}$	$\log K_{ML_2}$	$\log K_{MAL}$	$\log \beta_{MAL}$
HQSA	8.35	3.84	—	11.92	9.95	—	—	—
Gly	—	—	9.69	—	—	14.97	7.09	19.01
Ala	—	—	9.86	—	—	15.37	7.11	19.02
Phe	—	—	9.05	—	—	14.90	7.17	19.09

titrations curve of solution containing Cu(II) and HQSA (Curve 5, Fig. 1) in equimolar proportion exhibits two inflections, one sharp inflection at $m=2$ and another at $m=3$ (where m represent the moles of base added per mole of the metal ion). The curves for Cu(II)-Ala/Phe/Gly (1 : 1) systems (Curve 6-8, Fig. 1) also exhibit two inflections at $m=1$ and 2. In all these binary systems, the curves indicate the formation of 1 : 1 binary complexes in the lower pH range and their conversion into corresponding hydroxo derivatives at higher pH range.

Curves 9-11 (Fig. 1) represent the pH-metric titrations of copper nitrate in presence of equimolar concentrations of HQSA (H_2A) and one of the secondary ligands (Ala, Phe and Gly=HL) and exhibit only one inflection at $m=3$. Initially, all these curves run slightly above the corresponding 1 : 1 Cu(II) - HQSA titration curve. This may be due to the zwitter ion formation tendency of the α -amino acids and it indicates that initially Cu(II)-HQSA titration curve (Curve 5, Fig. 1), which is a measure of mixed ligand chelate formation occurs after $m=1.7, 1.8$ and 1.9 in Cu(II)-HQSA - Phe, Cu(II)-HQSA - Gly and Cu(II)-HQSA - Ala systems respectively. Comparison of these curves with corresponding composite curves [which can be drawn by adding the horizontal distance of the secondary ligand curve to the horizontal distance of Cu(II)-HQSA curve at the same pH] indicates the formation of 1 : 1 : 1 mixed ligand complex in overlapping steps.

The formation of 1 : 1 : 1 mixed ligand complex (ternary complex) may be represented as :

and overall reaction for the formation of ternary complex may be shown as :

If K' and K'' be the equilibrium constants of the reactions (i) and (ii) then

$$K' = \frac{[CuAL^-][H^+]}{[CuA][HL]} \quad \dots (1)$$

and

$$K'' = \frac{[CuAL^-][H^+]^3}{[Cu^{2+}][H_2A][HL]} \quad \dots (2)$$

Assuming that only mononuclear metal chelate species are formed in these systems, the following equations are obtained for maintaining the material balance :

$$T_M = [Cu^{2+}] + [CuA] + [CuAL^-] \quad \dots (3)$$

$$T_{OH} + [H^+] - [OH^-] = 2[CuA] + 3[CuAL^-] + [HA^-] + 2[A^{2-}] + [L^-] \quad \dots (4)$$

$$T_A = [H_2A] + [HA^-] + [A^{2-}] + [CuA] + [CuAL^-] \quad \dots (5)$$

$$T_L = [HL] + [L^-] + [CuAL^-] \quad \dots (6)$$

where T_M, T_A and T_L represent the total concentration of all the metal, primary and secondary ligands species respectively and T_{OH} is the concentration of the base added to the reaction mixture during titration. In a 1 : 1 : 1 reaction mixture, using the equations (3)-(6) and relations for the dissociation constants of ligands and equilibrium constant (K_1) of the reaction $Cu^{2+} + H_2A \rightleftharpoons CuA + 2H^+$, it may be shown under the experimental conditions viz. $T_M = T_A = T_L$ and $T_{OH} = m \cdot T_M$ that :

$$a[Cu^{2+}]^2 + b[Cu^{2+}] - c = 0 \quad \dots (7)$$

where, $a = K_1/[H^+]^2$, $b = x + (2 + k_1/[H^+])y$, $c = \{(3 - m)T_M - [H^+] + [OH^-]\}xy$, $x = 1 + k_1/[H^+] + k_1k_2/[H^+]^2$, $y = 1 + k'_1/[H^+]$ and $[H^+] = \text{antilog}(O - pH)$. k_1 and k_2 are the first and second dissociation constants of HQSA and k'_1 is the dissociation constant of α -amino acid.

The equilibrium concentration of free metal ions present in the reaction mixture was determined by solving equation (7). The concentration of other species involved in the equilibrium mixture were then calculated from the above equations and also the values of formation constants $\log K_{MAL}$ and $\log \beta_{MAL}$.

$$K_{MAL} = \frac{[CuAL^-]}{[CuA][L^-]} \quad \dots (8)$$

$$\beta_{MAL} = \frac{[CuAL^-]}{[Cu^{2+}][A^{2-}][L^-]} \quad \dots (9)$$

The constant values of chelate formation constant for the ternary systems viz. Cu(II)-HQSA - Gly, Cu(II)-HQSA - Ala and Cu(II)-HQSA - Phe were obtained in the acidic pH range i.e., between 4.09-5.52 ; 4.27-5.82 and 3.65 - 4.89 respectively. Therefore, the possibility of forming hydrolysed species has been ruled out in the pH range studied. It is also interesting to mention here that no precipitation occurs in ternary systems while in case of binary systems the precipitation occurs as indicated in Fig. 1. The values of formation constants of the resulting complexes are presented in Table 1.

The mixed ligand chelates formation is also supported by the colour change from greenish blue to dark green in the ternary systems. Further, it is

important to add that the values of $\log \beta_{MAL}$ for ternary complexes are higher than the mean of $\log K_{MA_2}$ and $\log K_{ML_2}$, indicating the higher stability of mixed complexes.

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Studies on the Stability of Trivalent Lanthanum Complexes with Catechol

B. C. BHUYAN and S. N. DUBEY*

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University,
Kurukshetra-192 119, Haryana

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THE complexation reactions of catechol with La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III), Tb(III), Dy(III), Ho(III) and Y(III) have been studied potentiometrically at $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$ in aqueous solution with potassium nitrate as supporting electrolyte. The thermodynamic stability constants have been evaluated. The trend in the stability of these complexes has also been discussed.

A survey of the literature revealed that some studies¹⁻³ have been made on the complex formation ability of catechol with trivalent lanthanide ions. However, no attempt appears to have been made to determine the thermodynamic stability constants of the complexes of catechol with Ln(III). In view of the above, the present study deals with the determination of thermodynamic stability constants of La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III), Tb(III), Dy(III), Ho(III) and Y(III) complexes with catechol by extrapolating the determined formation constants at different ionic strengths (0.05, 0.2 and 0.35M, 25°) to zero ionic strength. The experimental technique used was that of Calvin and Bjerrum^{4,5} as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁶.

Experimental

Materials: The lanthanide nitrates (Indian Rare Earths Ltd.) were dissolved in double distilled water and standardized by oxalate method⁷. All other reagents used were of AR grade.

Apparatus: A Philips pH meter (PR 9405M) fitted with glass and calomel electrodes was used

*To whom correspondence should be addressed.

for measuring pH. The instrument was standardized by using BDH buffer tablets of pH 4 and 9.2.

Procedure: Three solutions (total volume 50 ml in each case) of following compositions were prepared: $3.91 \times 10^{-3}M$ nitric acid, $3.91 \times 10^{-3}M$ nitric acid + $3.0 \times 10^{-3}M$ ligand, and $3.91 \times 10^{-3}M$ nitric acid + $3.0 \times 10^{-3}M$ ligand + $5.0 \times 10^{-4}M$ metal. Appropriate amounts of potassium nitrate (2M) were added to maintain the desired ionic strengths.

The mixtures were thermostated at $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$ and were titrated pH metrically against a standard sodium hydroxide solution (0.6993M). For the sake of brevity titration curves obtained at $\mu = .05M$ ($25 \pm 0.5^\circ$) for La(III)-catechol system have only been given in Fig. 1 [the acid titration curve (A), ligand titration curve (B) and complex titration curve (C)].

Fig. 1. pH titration curves: A—Acid, B—Ligand, C—Complex titration curves; $\mu = 0.05M$ (KNO_3), 25° .

Results and Discussion

The protonation constants of the ligand and stepwise stability constants of metal ligand complexes were calculated as follows:

The \bar{n}_A values calculated at various pH values from acid and ligand titration curves using Irving and Rossotti equation⁶ were plotted against the values of pH. From the formation curves, the values of protonation constants obtained at half \bar{n}_A values were computed using computational techniques^{8,9}, viz., Pointwise calculation method, Correction term method and Curve fitting method. The mean values are given in Table 1.

The stepwise metal-ligand stability constants were calculated using ligand and complex titration